

Impact of Science Process - Based ... (Anyifite, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11484564>

Impact of Science Process - Based Approach on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of the science process-based approach on performance in biology among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. Two Research Questions and two Null Hypotheses guided the study and were tested at a $P \leq 0.05$ significance level. The pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental research design was used for the study. The study population consists of 3,929 (Male, 1,623 and Female, 2,306) senior secondary school class two (SS II) government secondary school biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of 133 (Male, 63 and Female, 70) were selected from the target population using a multistage sampling technique. The experimental group was taught the concepts of living in biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.), while the control group was taught using the lecture method. A validated instrument called the Biology Performance Test (B.P.T.) was used for data collection. The reliability of B.P.T. was assessed utilizing a test-retest reliability method. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistics was used for analysis, and the result produced a reliability coefficient of 0.86. Moreover, B.P.T. was validated by three (3) Senior Lecturers. Data collected were analyzed using mean rank and standard deviation for the research questions, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) were used to analyze the Null hypotheses; the study revealed that Students taught using S.P.B.A. performed significantly better in their academic performance in favour of the high experimental group than those taught using lecture method; Male and Female Students taught using S.P.B.A. did not perform significantly different in their academic performance in all the varied ability groups from those taught using lecture method. In light of these findings, S.P.B.A. instructional strategies enhanced the academic performance in the concept taught in Biology. This study, amongst others, concludes that S.P.B.A. training should be organized for biology teachers through workshops to equip them with learning and integrate it into lessons in some biology concepts to enhance students' academic performance and varied abilities.

Keywords: Process-Based Approach, Performance, Biology, Varied Ability.

Introduction

The teaching and learning science subjects present challenges across educational systems globally, including Nigeria. Various factors contribute to these challenges, such as poor quality of students admitted, population explosion, inadequate teaching and learning facilities, and ineffective teaching strategies (Ahmed, 2014; Ahmed, 2014). Notably, teaching strategies, particularly in science education, have been a focus of concern among educators. Research indicates that hands-on science instruction and cooperative learning approaches significantly enhance students' science performance and attitudes towards the subject (Felita, 2018). Academic performance is often measured by the extent of knowledge acquisition and mastery of skills resulting from instruction or training (Usman, 2010). Understanding science concepts goes beyond mere recall; it involves actively manipulating and applying knowledge (Cavallo & Lauback, 2021; Ahmed, 2014).

Biology education, a critical component of science education in Nigeria, aims to equip students with knowledge and skills to understand the natural world and prepare them for the workforce (Haruna, 2019; N.E.R.D.C., 2013). However, challenges persist, with students' achievement in biology examinations declining due to inadequate teaching methods and emphasis on theoretical presentation over practical aspects (Nsofor & Dada, 2013; Maikano, 2016). A shift towards a process-based approach to teaching biology is recommended to address these challenges. This approach emphasizes acquiring science process skills alongside conceptual knowledge, enabling students to learn actively and retain information effectively (Danjuma, 2017). As proposed by Piaget, constructivist theory underpins this approach, viewing learning as an active process where students construct knowledge based on their experiences and existing understanding (Danjuma, 2017; Maikano, 2016).

In light of these considerations, this study investigates the impact of the Science Process-Based Approach on the performance of secondary school biology students with varied abilities in Zaria, Nigeria. By adopting a constructivist perspective and

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integrating science process skills into teaching, the study aims to enhance students' learning experiences and academic achievement in biology.

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite biology's significance and popularity among Nigerian students, performance at the senior secondary school level could be consistently better (Ahmed, 2014). This trend raises concerns about potential workforce shortages in science and technology-related fields. Inadequate teaching methods employed by teachers in Nigeria's senior secondary schools significantly contribute to this poor performance (Ahmed & Abimbola, 2011; Umar, 2011). Rote learning is prevalent, where students memorize information without gaining a deep understanding of the subject matter. Biology students' performance in the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (S.S.S.C.E.) in Kaduna state, Nigeria, reflects this issue.

The statistical table of Biology results in the May/June West African Examination S.S.C.E. in Kaduna State, Nigeria, shows students' performance.

Table 1.1 Students' Performances in Biology in Kaduna State W.A.E.C. May/June 2016-2022

Year	Total Sat	No with A1-C6	% with A1-C6	No with D7-F9	% with D7-F9
2016	126,821	59657	47.04	67161	52.96
2017	134,852	56570	41.95	78282	58.05
2018	130,653	56155	42.98	74498	57.02
2019	150,925	72204	47.85	78722	52.17
2020	143,936	62008	43.08	81928	56.92
2021	149,162	61028	40.90	88134	59.10
2022	136,916	58284	42.60	78632	57.40

Source: West African Examination Office, Kaduna Office (2022).

Over the past seven years (2016-2022), the percentage of students passing biology at credit level (A1-C6) in the examination conducted by the West African Examination Council (W.A.E.C., 2022) consistently remained below 50% (West African Examination Council, 2022). This decline underscores the need for interventions that promote effective, activity-based, and learner-centred teaching and learning approaches.

Addressing the low performance of students in biology requires identifying and addressing various factors, including teaching methods, learning materials, teacher factors, societal influences, and instructional strategies. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the Impact of the Science Process - Approach on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the study

1. This study aims to investigate the academic performance of students with varied ability levels who were taught Biology concepts using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.
2. To determine the academic performance of Male and female students with varied ability levels who were taught Biology concepts using a Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in mean performance scores between students with varied abilities taught biology concepts using the Science Process Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the lecture method?
2. What is the difference in mean Performance scores of male and female students with varied abilities who were taught biology concepts using a Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students with varied ability levels who were taught Biology concepts using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.
2. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between male and female students with varied ability levels who were taught biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.

Methodology

The pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental research design was used for the study, which involved two coeducational secondary schools and two classes in the Zaria educational zone, Kaduna State. The study population consists of 3 929 (Male, 1,623 and Female, 2,306) senior secondary school class two (SS II) government secondary school biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of 133 (Male, 63 and Female, 70) were

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selected from the target population using a multistage sampling technique. The researcher designed the Biology Performance Test (B.P.T.) to measure the performance of students exposed to S.P.B.A. in Biology. The test consisted of 50 multiple-choice questions designed to measure academic performance in the concept of living taught, and it was used as the instrument for data collection. Pretests were administered before exposing the experimental group to the Science Process-Based Approach, with schools randomly assigned to experimental and Control groups. By the categorization that Ajewole and Okebukola had developed, the subjects were categorized according to their ability levels. The reliability of B.P.T. was assessed utilizing a test-retest reliability method. The first test was given, and after two weeks, a retest was administered to a different school that was not part of the school selected for the research. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistics was used for analysis, and the result produced a reliability coefficient of 0.86; after a five-week teaching period, a posttest using the B.P.T. was administered, a posttest using the B.P.T. was administered, and data were analyzed using Mean, Standard deviation, ANOVA, ANCOVA, and Kruskal Wallis to answer research questions and hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in mean performance scores of students with varied abilities who are taught Biology concepts using a Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method?

Table 1 Mean and Standard Deviation of Students Performance Test Scores in Experimental and Control Group

Ability Levels	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	MD
Low	Experimental	16	25.69	3.81	5.69
	Control	18	20.00	5.13	
Medium	Experimental	31	33.06	2.11	5.68
	Control	34	27.38	3.24	
High	Experimental	16	39.06	3.87	9.00
	Control	18	30.06	3.47	

The data presented in Table 1 indicates that the experimental and Control groups differed significantly across varied ability levels. Specifically, the experimental group exhibited a mean score of 25.69 for students with low ability levels, whereas the control group had a mean score of 20.00, resulting in a mean difference of 5.69. Among students with medium ability levels, the experimental group had a mean score of 33.06, compared to 27.38 for the control group, yielding a mean difference of 5.68. In contrast, the experimental group achieved a mean score of 39.06 for students with high ability levels, while the control group scored 30.06, resulting in a mean difference of 9.00. Hence, the analysis reveals that the mean difference is most pronounced among students with high ability levels, with a value of 9.00, followed by those with low ability levels, with a mean difference of 5.69 and medium ability levels, with a mean difference of 5.68.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in mean Performance scores of male and female students with varied abilities who are taught biology concepts using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method?

Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Performance Test Scores in Experimental and Control Groups.

Ability Levels	Groups	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	MD
Low	Experimental	Male	7	28.86	1.07	5.64
		Female	9	23.22	3.27	
	Control	Male	9	21.56	1.24	3.12
		Female	9	18.44	7.00	

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Medium	Experimental	Male	10	35.08	0.79	3.29
		Female	19	31.79	1.62	
High	Control	Male	18	27.78	1.70	0.84
		Female	16	26.94	4.4	
	Experimental	Male	10	39.30	4.55	0.63
		Female	8	38.67	2.73	
Control	Male	9	31.33	3.28	2.55	
	Female	9	28.78	3.35		

The findings presented in Table 2 illustrate that in the Experimental group, students with low abilities, both male and female, achieved performance scores of 28.86 and 23.22, respectively, resulting in a mean difference of 5.64. Among those with medium skills, male and female students attained performance scores of 35.08 and 31.79, respectively, yielding a mean difference of 3.29. For students with high skills, male and female participants scored 39.30 and 38.67, respectively, resulting in a mean difference of 0.63.

In contrast, in the Control group, male and female students with low abilities achieved performance scores of 21.56 and 18.44, respectively, with a mean difference of 3.12. Among those with medium skills, male and female students scored 27.78 and 26.94, respectively, resulting in a mean difference of 0.84. Finally, male and female participants attained performance scores of 31.33 and 28.78 for students with high abilities, respectively, resulting in a mean difference of 2.55. Consequently, the mean difference is highest among low-ability students in the experimental group, both male and female, with a value of 5.64, and lowest among high-ability students in the experimental group, both male and female, with a value of 0.63.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students with varied ability levels who are taught Biology concepts using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.

Table 3 (a) one - way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results of Students Performance in Experimental and Control groups

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	f-crit.	P
Between Groups	3865.036	5	773.007	62.323	3.00	0.000
Within Groups	1575.220	127	12.403			
Total	5440.256	132				

$\alpha \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Fieldwork (2019)

In Table 3 (a), the analysis indicated a calculated P-value of 0.000, which is lower than the 0.05 significance level, and a computed F-value of 62.323, which exceeds the 3.00 F-critical value. These results indicate significant differences in performance mean scores among the varied ability students taught Biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (Experimental) and Lecture (Control) methods. Consequently, the null hypothesis is currently rejected, stating that there is no significant difference in performance mean scores among varied ability students taught Biology using the Science Process-Based Approach and Lecture method. Furthermore, the interpretation from Table 3 (a) demonstrates that significant differences exist in performance mean scores among the varied ability students taught Biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (Experimental) and Lecture (Control) methods. The data underwent a post-hoc test using Scheffe's test to establish the significance level, as shown in Table 3(b).

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Table 3 (b) posthoc Scheffe's Result of Students Performance in Experimental and Control groups

Groupings		N	Subset for alpha = 0.05				
			1	2	3	4	5
Low	Experimental	16		25.6875			
	Control	18	20.0000				
Medium	Experimental	31				33.0556	
	Control	34		27.3824	27.3824		
High	Experimental	16					39.0625
	Control	18			30.0556	30.0556	
Sig.			1.000	.800	.332	.204	1.000

In Table 3 (b), the Post Hoc analysis using the Scheffe test on performance revealed that the low control group, with a mean score of 20.0000, belongs to the minor subset. Following this, the low experimental group, with a mean score of 25.6875, and the medium control group, with a mean score of 27.3824, are categorized under subset 2. In subset 3, the high control group, with a mean score of 30.0556, is contrasted with the medium experimental group, with a mean score of 33.0556. Notably, the high experimental group, with a mean score of 39.0625, is significantly higher in subset 5, indicating the highest performance among all subsets.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between Male and female students with varied ability levels who are taught biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method.

Table 4: ANCOVA results of students' Male and Female Performance in Experimental and Control groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Corrected mode	4150.286	11	377.299	35.391	0.000
Intercept	101488.575	1	101488.575	9519.698	0.000
Groups	1453.346	1	1453.346	136.325	0.000
Gender	211.808	1	211.808	19.868	0.000
Ability	2286.115	2	1143.058	107.220	0.000
Groups* Gender	7.657	1	7.657	0.718	0.398
Groups* Ability	50.086	2	25.043	2.349	0.100
Gender*Ability	39.059	2	19.530	1.832	0.165
Groups* Gender*Ability	29.588	2	14.794	1.388	0.254
Error	1289.969	121	10.661		
Total	119391.000	133			
Corrected Total	5440.256	132			

$\alpha \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Fieldwork (2019)

Table 4 indicates that the computed P-value for groups versus performance ability levels is 0.100, which exceeds the significance level of 0.05. Similarly, the calculated P-value for performance ability levels versus gender is 0.165, surpassing the 0.05 alpha significance level. Additionally, the computed P-value for groups versus performance ability levels versus gender is 0.254, higher than the 0.05 alpha significance level. These results suggest no significant differences in performance mean scores among male and female students of varied abilities taught biology using the Science Process-Based Approach and Lecture Method. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states no significant difference in mean performance scores of Male and female students with varied ability levels taught biology using the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) and those exposed to the Lecture Method, is retained.

Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the impact of the Science Process-Based Approach on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Zaria educational Zone, Kaduna State. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested based on the subjects'

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scores obtained in Performance and Varied abilities of students' Concept of Living in S.S.I.I. Biology. The findings are discussed as follows:

The significant difference in performance observed can be attributed to the interrelated nature of science concepts and processes, as Mari (2012) noted. Understanding science concepts is only possible with knowledge of the processes used to generate knowledge. The superior success of the experimental group over the lecture group in academic performance can be further attributed to the in-depth teaching and thorough explanation of living concepts during the research. These findings are supported by Sani (2017), Ibrahim (2012), Gadzama (2012), and Shafiu (2014), who asserted in their separate studies that the experimental group exposed to the Science Process-Based Approach performed significantly better than the control group. The activities involved in the S.P.B.A. motivate learners to learn and concentrate on the concepts being taught and provide avenues for meaningful learning, thus enhancing students' academic performance.

Regarding gender's relationship to academic performance, this study reveals that the performance of male and female subjects in the experimental and Control groups is not significantly the same, implying that the Science Process-Based Approach is not gender-friendly. This finding agrees with Sani (2017) and Anaso (2008), who noted in their studies that gender did not significantly affect students' academic achievement in their subjects. Similarly, Agommuoh and Nzewi (2013) and Babajide (2020) observed no significant influence of gender on students' academic achievement in science. However, Nwosu (2008) and Ibrahim (2012) disagreed with the findings of this study. They concluded that a significant difference exists in academic achievement involving activities for both boys and girls, yielding more effective learning irrespective of ability levels. The existence of gender differences in academic achievement refutes the assertion of Afuwape and Olupide (2008) and Ogunleye and Babajide (2011), who remarked in their studies that the era of male supremacy and dominance in science learning was fast winding up. The reasons for the lack of significant difference in academic performance in gender for experimental and Control groups account for the difference because of the area of research and the population involved compared to those who advanced significant differences between gender groups.

Conclusion

The Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.) has emerged as a pedagogical framework to enhance students' academic performance by promoting active learning and critical thinking skills. It emphasizes inquiry-based learning, where students actively engage in the scientific process through observation, experimentation, and analysis. Studies have shown that S.P.B.A. can effectively promote the learning of complex scientific concepts by providing students with hands-on experiences and opportunities for exploration. However, despite its potential benefits, research suggests that the effectiveness of S.P.B.A. may vary across different student populations and contexts. While some studies have reported positive outcomes, others have found limited or no improvement in student performance compared to traditional lecture-based methods. Factors such as teacher training, classroom environment, and student engagement levels can influence the success of S.P.B.A. implementation.

Furthermore, gender differences in learning styles and preferences may impact the effectiveness of S.P.B.A. for male and female students. Research has shown that males and females may respond differently to specific instructional methods, with factors such as confidence levels, spatial reasoning abilities, and socialization playing a role. Therefore, it is essential to consider gender-specific needs and preferences when designing and implementing instructional approaches like S.P.B.A. While S.P.B.A. holds promise for promoting the learning of Biology concepts, its effectiveness may vary across different student populations and genders. Further research is needed to explore the factors influencing the success of S.P.B.A. implementation and to develop strategies for enhancing its efficacy for all students, regardless of gender or ability level.

Recommendations

1. Educators should tailor instructional strategies, including the Science Process-Based Approach (S.P.B.A.), to meet students' diverse learning needs and preferences, taking into account factors such as gender, ability level, and prior knowledge.
2. School administrators and policymakers should prioritize professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their pedagogical skills and knowledge of practical instructional approaches, such as S.P.B.A.

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